

Analyzing Geopolitical Risk Connectedness in Emerging Countries with a Focus on U.S. Influence

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Abstract

The study unveils the static and dynamic network of global GPR among US and emerging markets. We examine connectedness in GPR of US and emerging countries using DY and BK approaches on data from January 1985 until June 2020. In the time-frequency domain framework, we construct dependency network and minimal spanning tree (MST). Results show some interesting bi-directional links, especially countries with close proximity have higher spillover and US is a big transmitter (size of the node in network shows importance and also central position in MST figures) of GPR, and almost influence all emerging countries' GPR. The evidence of time-varying analysis shows that nature of GPR network has changed overtime. Finally, we also show that GPR transmission tends to be stronger during times of escalated political tensions. The findings have important implications related to ongoing debate about policy environment and leading role of US for global geopolitics.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Geopolitical events like terrorism, wars and international conflicts receive immense media coverage. In general, geopolitical conflicts within and between countries give rise to disturbed socio-economic conditions (Balli et al., 2019). Often major political events significantly influence economy, financial markets and sentiments of market agents (Fielding, 2003; Gaibulloev & Sandler, 2008; Bialkowski et al. 2008; Wolfers & Zitzewitz, 2009). Fluctuations in the political scene give rise to elevated levels of uncertainty and risks that leave a notable mark on the performance of firms and financial markets. In particular, emerging economies are often vulnerable to dramatic variations in trade and capital that are time and again attributed to GPR (Cheng & Chiu, 2017).

In today's world, with advancement in information technology and social media, the information flows across countries have increased at unprecedented level. Moreover, increased information flows between countries have led to higher level of international interdependence and drop in information asymmetries. Consequently, international information flows associated with GPR are also peaking, which stimulate synchronized behavior of financial markets and economic agents across countries. In addition, the literature on conflict contagion also recognized the functional role of information flows in propagating geopolitical conflicts across nations (Beiser, 2011; Beiser, 2013; Weidmann, 2015). Where, media information plays a significant role in transmitting information related to specific geopolitical events like civil armed conflicts, ethnic and political violence, etc. Hence, this phenomenon creates strong GPR transmission in form of information flows across borders similar to other forms of information transmission such as economic policy

uncertainty, stock

volatility and economic reforms.

A key thing to highlight is that most of the existing literature focuses on the impact of GPR on different macro-economic variables like tourism, oil, stock etc. However, GPR transmission between countries also has crucial implications for national security, investors and financial sector. Pointing towards this fact, many reports by international financial institutions (for instance, Global Risk report and World Economic Outlook) highlight the contagious nature of GPR and its consequences for investors, corporate managers and policy formulators. Accordingly, understanding the cross country linkages of GRP transmission is particularly important for emerging economies to avoid geopolitical shocks. Since prior research has shown that emerging economies suffer more due to exogenous shocks in comparison to developed countries (Carriere-Swallow & Cespedes, 2013). Also, lately due to the strong economic performance of emerging markets like China, Korea, etc. international investors are attracted towards profitable opportunities in emerging economies. However, such investments are also likely to encounter downsides which are associated with transmission of international shocks like GPR. Moreover, the systematic nature of geopolitical uncertainty has more dire effects in emerging markets because they are more fragile than developed markets (Hoque & Zaidi, 2020). This is further validated by International Monetary Fund (IMF) that term geopolitical risk as salient risk for global economic outlook (International Monetary Fund, 2017).

In the post globalization era when countries are highly connected in terms of economy, trade, and international relations being the geopolitical superpower US has a functional role in channeling GPR shocks to emerging markets. Considering US as the military, economic and political leaders of the world,

geopolitical shocks originated in US are always likely to create new risks and escalate existing risks for global economy and international relations (Gupta et al., 2019). Although, the earlier literature on geopolitical conflicts has generally discussed the spread, diffusion and contagion of geopolitical events in physical form (Blomberg & Rosendorff, 2006; Buhaug & Gleditsch, 2008; Braithwaite, 2010). However, little evidence prevails on GPR transmission in form of information flows. Surprising no study examines how GPR in one country influence GPR in another and our focus is on emerging countries because those are more volatile in terms of GPR. We also focus how GPR in US impacts GPR in emerging countries. To best of our knowledge, we are the first ones to examine time-frequency domain based connectedness of GPR among US and emerging markets. For this purpose we employ Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) [DY] time-domain approach and Barunik and Krehlik (2018) [BK] frequency-domain approach. Further, we use GPR indexes constructed by Caldara and Iacoviello (2018) as proxy of geopolitical risks.

The findings of the study reveal meaningful bi-directional GPR links among US and emerging markets. In particular, countries with close proximity have higher spillover and US as the dominant transmitter of GPR, and almost influence all emerging countries' GPR. The findings highlight the central role of US in global geopolitical network.

In the following section data and methodology are described. The section 3 presents the results and findings of the study. The last section concludes the paper.

Data and Methodology

Our sample consists of GPR series of USA and nineteen emerging economies namely, Argentina, Brazil, China, Columbia, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Israel, Korea, Malaysia, Mexico, Philippines, Russia, Saudi

Arab, South Africa, Thailand, Turkey, Venezuela and Ukraine. Monthly data of GPR indexes is collected for the time period starting from 1, January, 1985 to 30, June, 2020. The sample selection reflects reasonable and meaningful sample size to develop global network of GPR. The summary statistics are not reported due to space consideration¹.

In order to detect GPR spillovers between US and emerging economies, we use Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) time-domain approach and Barunik and Krehlik (2018) frequency-domain approach. Using the underlying methods two different GPR networks, dependency network analysis and Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) are formulated. Both approaches allow us to document interdependence between the GPRs. In addition, it also captures the risk transmission and information dependence in the network. The brief description of DY and BK approaches is as follows.

The study follows Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) to measure spillovers between US and emerging markets in the generalized VAR framework presented by Pesaran and Shin (1998). Let's assume a VAR (p), $y_t = \pi \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i y_{t-i} + u_t$ model, where $N \times 1$ endogenous vector of variables is denoted as y_i and u_t represents vector of error terms distributed independently and identically. Hence, the spillovers in this framework are described as the H-step ahead generalized forecast error variance decomposition and expressed in a following way:

$$\phi_{IJ}(H) = \frac{\zeta_{jj}^{-1} \sum_{h=0}^{H-1} (\hat{e}_i C_h \Sigma e_j)^2}{\sum_{h=0}^{H-1} (\hat{e}_i C_h \Sigma A^h e_i)} \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, Σ is the variance matrix and for j^{th} equation ζ_{jj} is the standard deviation of the error term. Also, e_i is the selection vector with 1 as the i^{th} element and 0 otherwise. Finally, the net-pairwise spillover

¹ The results can be made available upon request.

between market (i) to market (j) is defined in the following way:

$$\text{NPS}_{ij}(H) = \left(\frac{\phi_{ji}^{\sim}(H)}{\sum_{i,Q=1}^N \phi_{iq}^{\sim}(H)} \right) - \left(\frac{\phi_{ji}^{\sim}(H)}{\sum_{i,Q=1}^N \phi_{jq}^{\sim}(H)} \right) \times 100, \phi_{ij}^{\sim}(H) = \frac{\phi_{ij}(H)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \phi_{ij}(H)} \quad (2)$$

Following the work of Diebold and Yilmaz (2012, 15), Barunik and Krehlik (2018) propose frequency-domain approach to account for the frequency dynamics (long, medium and short terms) in measuring spillovers. In this approach spectral representation of generalized forecast error variance decomposition is used to measure spillovers at different frequency bands. For instance, at a given frequency band $f = (a, b)$ the aggregate measure can be described as follows:

$$C^f = c^f \cdot \Gamma(f) \quad (3)$$

In the equation (3), the spectral weight $\Gamma(f) = \frac{\sum_{i,j=1}^N (v_f^i)_{i,j}}{\sum_{i,j} (v_f^i)_{i,j}}$ and C^f is the total spillover measure on the spillover tables (v_f^i) corresponding to desired frequency $f = (a, b)$.

Empirical Results and Findings

Empirical results Using DY Approach

In order to study the GPR spillovers between U.S and emerging markets, we first construct state-of-art global network of GPR connectedness using Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) time-domain approach. The complete graphical illustration of the network is displayed in Fig.1. The analysis reveals various meaningful insights about the nature of GPR linkages between US and emerging economies. We present dependency network analysis diagram of GPR in Fig. 1.

<< **Figure 1 about here** >>

Firstly, the findings depict the central role of U.S geopolitical policies for global GPR network since GPR in emerging economies is significantly linked with US GPR. The findings also show that US is the largest transmitter of informational spillovers in our sample. This again highlights that the

geopolitical

uncertainty in US dominates global geopolitics. Moreover, the evidence suggest that US strongly propagates GPR shocks to emerging economies, which then have a crucial impact on the global geopolitical temperature. However, the evidence indicates no strong bilateral transmission of GPR from US to any particular emerging market in our sample.

Second, the evidence also shows that emerging economies including China, Saudi Arab, Ukraine, Venezuela and Brazil also play an important role in propagating geopolitical shocks to other emerging markets. On the other side, the remaining emerging markets are recipient of geopolitical informational spillovers. In addition, the evidence also exhibits strong geographical GPR connections between the emerging markets. For instance, we find strong bilateral GPR connection between China-Hong Kong, Brazil- Argentina, Malaysia-Indonesia, Russia- Ukraine and Saudi Arab-Israel. Furthermore, interestingly we also found few cases of strong GRP connectedness based on geopolitical conflicts between certain countries like Saudi Arab- Turkey, Israel-Saudi Arab and China-Hong Kong. Finally, the evidence also shows that Thailand is the least connected country with other emerging markets in terms of GPR spillovers.

<< **Figure 2 about here** >>

Next, we calculate full sample MTS to measure the total connectedness in GPR system using Diebold-Yilmaz framework. The MTS of GPR is presented in Fig.2. The findings corroborate the previous evidence. Similar to dependency network analysis, the centrality analysis also highlights crucial insights about the GPR linkages between US and emerging markets. The results show some interesting bi-directional links, especially countries with close proximity have higher spillover and US is a big transmitter (size of the node in network shows importance and

also central position in MST figures) of GPR, and almost influences all emerging countries' GPR. The GPR of six emerging markets is directly linked to US policy and in rest of the markets root shock of US geopolitical risk is transmitted via China, Mexico, Venezuela and Saudi Arab. This also highlights that countries namely China, Mexico, Venezuela and Saudi Arab also play a crucial role in global GPR network. As already mentioned we find functional role of geographical connections in GPR spillovers since GPR spillovers between countries in the same region is strong. Likewise, we also detect a GPR cluster of Saudi Arab, Israel and Turkey which is intuitively based on regional geopolitical conflicts. Finally, the results exhibit that countries including Thailand, Ukraine, South Africa, Turkey and Israel are least connected with rest of countries in terms of GPR. Overall, the centrality analysis highlights the dominance of US on global geopolitics.

Our results may not be directly comparable with existing literature due to the novelty of the study. However, still, they offer important and new insights for the existing literature which highlights that US based newspaper indexes of macroeconomic shocks impact developed and emerging markets (Klößner & Sekkel, 2014; Caggiano et al., 2018; Das et al., 2019). For instance, Marfatia et al. (2020) find that US policy uncertainty is responsible for large fraction of spillovers to develop and emerging markets.

Empirical results Using BK Approach

Next we exhibit the dependency network and centrality analysis using Barunik and Krehlik (2018) frequency-domain approach. We calculate frequency based connectedness between geopolitical risk spillovers between US and emerging markets for short-run (1-6 months) and long-run (more than 6 months). The results of frequency-domain approach confirm the evidence presented in the earlier section.

<< Figure 3 about here >>

First, once again the short-run dependency network diagram exhibits the dominant role of US as a transmitter of geopolitical shocks to the emerging countries. The results also show that China, Russia and Saudi Arab are also net contributor of GPR shocks to other sample countries. In a way the findings validate the prominence of China and Russia as the two major countries after US dominating global geopolitics. Also, considering the importance of oil for global trade and economy, being the largest exporter of oil Saudi Arab also plays a crucial role in transmitting GPR shocks to other countries. The findings are in some way corroborated by Su et al. (2019), they find strong correlations between oil prices and geopolitical risk in the short-medium term in frequency –domain framework for Saudi Arab. Again, the results also illustrate strong GPR spillovers between the countries with close proximity. However, we find weak bilateral GPR spillovers between sample countries in short-run dependency Network diagram.

The long-run results show that US, China, Saudi Arab, Brazil, Venezuela and Ukraine are net contributor of GPR spillovers to other countries. Here, interestingly the evidence highlights political instability in Venezuela and Ukraine has profound impact on global geopolitics as both countries emerge as prominent transmitter of GPR shocks to US and other emerging markets. Further, the findings also verify political nexus of Russia-Ukraine since we find strong bilateral GPR spillovers between both countries in the long-run. Furthermore, the results again confirm the role of geographical connections in strengthening GPR spillovers between countries. Overall, the findings reveal heterogeneity between our short-term and long-term GPR connectedness. The results clearly support that GPR spillovers between US and emerging markets more often than not

is a long-run phenomenon and the GPR linkages in the short-run are relatively weak. The idea is also corroborated by Tiwari et al. (2019), who also suggest that geopolitical risks have more profound implications in the long-term.

<< **Figure 4 about here** >>

Next, we present short-long term results of MST in Fig. 4. As it can be seen, the short-run MST constructed in frequency-domain framework is exactly the same as one formulated using DY approach. As evident from results degree centrality is highest for US with six nodes which shows that GPR of emerging markets is most connected with US geopolitics. In addition, China, Mexico, Venezuela and Saudi Arab also hold central role in global GPR network. Thailand is found to be the least connected country in terms of GPR connectedness. In the long-run interestingly Saudi Arab alongside US appears as the dominant country to transmit geopolitical shocks to rest of the emerging markets. Also, the role of China as the contributor of GPR also increases in the long term. Furthermore, in terms of Closeness centrality the GPR policies of US and China appear to be most connected which reinforces the notion that both countries are frontline competitors for global geopolitical leadership.

Dynamic Analysis using DY and BK Approach

We further extend our investigation to establish whether GPR connectedness between US and emerging economies vary over time? As the degree of connectedness in GPR network significantly depends upon the informational spillovers between countries, hence we argue that dynamic nature of informational spillovers will be detected in the global GPR network. In order to capture the time-varying characteristics of GPR spillovers, we calculate Dynamic rolling-window based spillover index of GPR using DY and BK approach.

<< **Figure 5 about here** >>

<< **Figure 6 about here** >>

The Fig. 5 illustrates the dynamic connectedness graph calculated using DY framework. As expected we can observe the time-varying nature of GPR spillovers between US and emerging markets. We find episodes of high GPR spillovers during major US and global events such as 9/11 attack in 2001, Afghan war 2002, Iraq invasion in 2003 and US-China trade war in 2019. The findings highlight the pivotal role of US geopolitical policies for geopolitical stability in emerging markets. Further, the higher level of GPR integration between US and emerging markets during times of escalated political tensions has also important economic implications. For example, higher transmissions of GPR shocks from US to emerging markets during these times imply low diversification opportunities and benefits for portfolio managers and investors.

Next, the Fig. 6 displays the short and long term GPR connectedness between US and emerging markets estimated using BK method. The results again corroborate the earlier evidence and show high GPR spillovers between the sample economies during important global geopolitical events. In addition, we also observe higher degree of GPR connectedness in the long run as compare to the short run. The findings depict that the influence of US geopolitical policy on the geopolitical environment of emerging economies is more pronounced in the long term. From the perspective of financial markets, the findings imply that prompt response of market participants to GPR shocks in the short run can offer diversification options in the emerging markets.

Conclusions

Understanding of the GPR transmission mechanism holds vital policy insights for corporate managers, market participants and national security advisers to formulate effective risk management policies and strategies. In order to fill this theoretical void this study sets out to examine GPR transmission among US and emerging markets. We examine time-frequency domain based connectedness of GPR among US and emerging markets using Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) [DY] time-domain approach and Barunik and Krehlik (2018) [BK] frequency-domain approach. We find strong bi-directional GPR interdependencies among emerging market. Our results also show global GPR network is significantly linked to US, which plays central role in transmitting GPR shocks to emerging markets. Further, we also find that GPR spillovers among US and emerging markets to some extent are related to geographical connections. Interestingly, we also note few cases of strong GPR spillovers between countries based on bi-lateral or regional conflicts. Finally, we also observe time-varying nature of GPR transmission, which tends to be stronger during times of escalated political tensions.

The findings have important implications for policy and financial markets. In terms of policy environment, the findings imply that the policy making process in emerging markets is not isolated and independent exercise. While, taking policy measures the policymakers should be aware of the close knit of GPR network and the dominating role of US in influencing global geopolitics. Also, the findings also manifest crucial role of policy makers to formulate prudent policies to minimize the adverse effects of GPR contagion, in particular for emerging economies. From the perspective of investors and portfolio managers findings highlight that GPR shocks transmit across markets which

can significantly affect portfolio allocation and diversification decisions. Moreover, the findings of the study conform to earlier evidence that indicates higher connectedness or interdependence between markets destroys benefits of international portfolio diversification and produces high risk transmission (Das et al., 2019). Further, the findings of the study are useful for businesses and institutions to better manage their credit risk, develop robust supply chains, and secure credit and political insurance and construct effective response plans to protect their businesses and assets from geopolitical surprises. For future research we also suggest further exploration on the determinants of GPR connectedness among emerging markets.

References

- Balli, F., Uddin, G. S., & Shahzad, S. J. H. (2019). Geopolitical risk and tourism demand in emerging economies. *Tourism Economics*, 25(6), 997-1005.
- Barunik, J., & Křehlík, T. (2018). Measuring the frequency dynamics of financial connectedness and systemic risk. *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, 16(2), 271-296.
- Beiser, J. (2011). *Looking Beyond Borders: Identification, Information, and Ethnic Conflict Contagion*. Technical report Working paper: University College London.
- Beiser, J. (2013). *Trampling out the spark? Governments' strategic reaction to the threat of ethnic conflict contagion* (Doctoral dissertation, PhD thesis. Working paper, University College London, UK).
- Białkowski, J., Gottschalk, K., & Wisniewski, T. P. (2008). Stock market volatility around national elections. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 32(9), 1941-1953.

- Blomberg, S. B., & Rosendorff, B. P. (2006). A gravity model of globalization, democracy and transnational terrorism. *USC CLEO Research Paper*, (C06-6).
- Braithwaite, A. (2010). Resisting infection: How state capacity conditions conflict contagion. *Journal of Peace Research*, 47(3), 311-319.
- Buhaug, H., & Gleditsch, K. S. (2008). Contagion or confusion? Why conflicts cluster in space. *International Studies Quarterly*, 52(2), 215-233.
- Caggiano, G., Castelnuovo, E., & Figueres, J. M. (2020). Economic policy uncertainty spillovers in booms and busts. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 82(1), 125-155.
- Carrière-Swallow, Y., & Céspedes, L. F. (2013). The impact of uncertainty shocks in emerging economies. *Journal of International Economics*, 90(2), 316-325.
- Cheng, C. H. J., & Chiu, C. W. J. (2018). How important are global geopolitical risks to emerging countries?. *International economics*, 156, 305-325.
- Das, D., Kannadhasan, M., & Bhattacharyya, M. (2019). Do the emerging stock markets react to international economic policy uncertainty, geopolitical risk and financial stress alike?. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 48, 1-19.
- Diebold, F. X., & Yilmaz, K. (2012). Better to give than to receive: Predictive directional measurement of volatility spillovers. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 28(1), 57-66.
- Diebold, F. X., & Yilmaz, K. (2015). Trans-Atlantic equity volatility connectedness: US and European financial institutions, 2004–2014. *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, 14(1), 81-127.
- Fielding, D. (2003). Modelling political instability and economic performance: Israeli investment during the Intifada. *Economica*, 70(277), 159-186.
- Gaibullov, K., & Sandler, T. (2008). Growth consequences of terrorism in Western Europe. *Kyklos*, 61(3), 411-424.
- International Monetary Fund. (2017). *World Economic Outlook October 2017: Seeking sustainable growth: short-term recovery, long-term challenges*. Washington, D.C: International Monetary Fund.
- Klößner, S., & Sekkel, R. (2014). International spillovers of policy uncertainty. *Economics Letters*, 124(3), 508-512.
- Marfatia, H., Zhao, W. L., & Ji, Q. (2020). Uncovering the global network of economic policy uncertainty. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 101223.
- Pesaran, H. H., & Shin, Y. (1998). Generalized impulse response analysis in linear multivariate models. *Economics letters*, 58(1), 17-29.
- Su, C. W., Khan, K., Tao, R., & Nicoleta-Claudia, M. (2019). Does geopolitical risk strengthen or depress oil prices and financial liquidity? Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Energy*, 187, 116003.
- Wolfers, J., & Zitzewitz, E. (2009). Using markets to inform policy: The case of the Iraq war. *Economica*, 76(302), 225-250.

Figure 1
Network diagram of spillover table based on DY approach

Lag = 1 month based on HQ criteria. Forecast horizon is 12 months.

Note: This network graph illustrates the degree of total connectedness in a system that consists of the 20 GPR series over the full sample period. Total connectedness is measured using the Diebold-Yilmaz framework. The size of the node shows the magnitude of contribution of each variable to system connectedness, while the color indicates the origin of connectedness. In particular, the red color implies contribution from the variable under consideration to the other variables of the system and the green color means contribution from the other variables to the variable under analysis. The color and shape of the arrows refer to the strength of connectedness. The red color and full line arrows represent strong spillovers while green and blue color arrows show medium and weak spillovers, respectively.

Figure 2
Minimum spanning tree (MST) of spillover table based on DY approach

Figure 3 Network diagram of frequency-domain spillover table based on BK approach A. Short-run (1-6 months)

Long-run (more than 6 months)

Figure 4
Minimum spanning tree (MST) of frequency domain spillover table based on BK approach
A. Short-run (1-6 months)

Long-run (more than 6 months)

Figure 5
Dynamic rolling-window based spillover

Note: Rolling window length is 100 months.

Figure 6
Dynamic rolling-window based frequency domain spillover index of GPR using BK approach

Note: Rolling window length is 100 months.